

The shade time travelling clock, the elemental time travelling clock, the decision time travelling clock, and the reason time travelling clock are in a day time twin paradox with each other, and goes as followed:

- If paired shade time travelling clock with elemental time travelling clock, then decision time travelling clock, however, if decision time travelling clock, then reason time travelling clock, however, if reason time travelling clock, then paired shade time travelling clock with elemental time travelling clock.

In the day time twin paradox shown explained and shown above, the shade time travelling clock is paired with the elemental time travelling clock, the decision time travelling clock is the extra, and the reason time travelling clock is the outcome of that day time twin paradox, where the name of this day time twin paradox explained and shown above is the environment day time twin paradox.

This set is timed as 1:30, and is dated as the 10th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.